

Appendix 9 AMIA Membership Demographics

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Table 1. AMIA Membership by Race and Ethnicity as of 04-19-2021

Race and Ethnicity	Number	Percentage
White	1711	40.88%
Not Specified	1298	31.02%
Asian	597	14.27%
Prefer not to answer	287	6.86%
Black or African American	130	3.11%
Multiracial	32	0.76%
Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	9	0.22%
American Indian or Alaska Native	5	0.12%
Other	2	0.05%
Hispanic/Latinx (may be of any race)	114	2.72%
Total	4185	100.00%

Table 2. AMIA Membership by Gender as of 04-19-2021

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	2122	50.70%
Female	1279	30.56%
Not Specified	717	17.13%
Prefer not to Answer	60	1.43%
Non-Binary	6	0.14%
Other	1	0.02%
Total	4185	100.00%